

VITILIGO (SHWITRA): A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW FROM AYURVEDIC AND MODERN PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

Vitiligo is a globally prevalent dermatological disorder that carries considerable social stigma. It is characterized by the development of white patches on the skin due to the loss or destruction of melanin pigment. The condition can appear on any part of the body, leading to visible discolouration and cosmetic imbalance, which often results in psychological distress and social embarrassment for the affected individuals. In Āyurveda, this disorder is classified under Kushta (dermatosis) and is referred to as Shwitra or Kilāsa. The present study aims to compile the scattered knowledge regarding Shwitra from classical Ayurvedic texts and to present a systematic and critical analysis of its concept and management as described in Ayurvedic science (Vitiligo). An effort has been made to systematically compile and present the scattered knowledge about Shwitra available in various Ayurvedic texts, with the objective of critically analyzing its concept and management as explained in Ayurvedic science (Vitiligo).

KEYWORDS: Shwitra, Kilasa, Kushta, Vitiligo, Leucoderma,

Ayurvedic management.

AIM

To critically analyze and compile the concept and management of Shwitra (Vitiligo) as described in classical Ayurvedic texts, and to correlate it with the modern understanding of Vitiligo.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the ancient science of life, emphasizes a holistic approach to health by maintaining balance between Sharira (body), Manas (mind), and Atma (spirit). It focuses on treating the root cause rather than just symptoms, making it effective for chronic skin disorders. Ayurvedic formulations, derived from natural herbs and minerals, are safe, time-tested, and restore internal balance through multiple mechanisms. Shwitra (Vitiligo) is a non-exudative skin disorder marked by white patches due to vitiation of Doshas, particularly Pitta and Rakta. Acharya Charaka described it as Raktaja Vikara involving Bhrajaka Pitta, responsible for normal skin pigmentation. When vitiated, it causes depigmentation. Though not listed among the 18 types of Kushtha, it becomes difficult to treat when deeper Dhatus are affected. Acharya Vagbhata regarded Shwitra as more severe than Kushtha, arising from Viruddha Ahara (incompatible food) and Papakarma.

According to Ayurveda, reduced Vyadhikshamatwa (immunity) plays a vital role in its pathogenesis. Modern medicine correlates Shwitra with Vitiligo, an autoimmune disorder causing melanocyte destruction and loss of skin pigment. It affects about 0.5–2% of the global population and around 4% in India,^[1] with no specific race or gender bias. Treatments like corticosteroids, immunomodulators, and phototherapy offer variable results.

Methods

Paribhasha (Definition)

In Ayurvedic texts, Shwitra and Kilāsa are mostly described as synonymous, though a few scholars consider them distinct varieties. Despite differences in description, all classical sources agree that Shwitra denotes a whitish discolouration of the skin. It is defined as a form of Kushta characterized by non-exudative (Aparisrāvi)^[2] white or hypopigmented patches on the skin.

From a modern medical perspective, Shwitra can be correlated with Vitiligo or Leucoderma, an autoimmune condition resulting in depigmentation of the skin. It presents as well-defined, pale or milky-white macules of variable size and distribution, which may also affect hair and

mucosal areas. The progression and extent of depigmentation are uncertain and vary among individuals.

Synonyms: Kilāsam, Pālitam, Kilāsi, Alasa, Dārūna, Arūna, Shwitra, Pāndura Kustha, Twak Puspī, Sidhmali, and Shweta Kushtam. Biomedical correlations include Vitiligo, Leucoderma, Achromoderma, and Hypomelanosis.

Historical Review

Historical references to Shwitra appear across Vedic, classical, and medieval literature. Ancient texts such as Atharvaveda first mention remedies for Kilāsam (loss of normal skin color) and Pālitam (whitening of scalp hair) in Darila's commentary on Kau Sutra 26.22–24, with additional mentions in Rigveda (V.53.1), Vajaseneji Samhitā, Kathaka Samhitā, Taittiriya Brāhmana, Tandyā Mahābrāhmana, and Pānini Vyākaraṇa (5/12/129). Manu Samhitā (3/7) highlights social implications, prohibiting marriage with children of Shweta Kushtha patients. Classical Ayurvedic texts, including Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya, and Ashtanga Samgraha, describe its classification, prognosis, and treatment, often using Shwitra and Kilāsa synonymously. Medieval scholars such as Mādhavakara, Bhāvamishrā, Shārangadhara, Chakradatta, Yoga Ratnākara, Vangasena, and Kāshyapa provided further insights. References to the disease are also found in Agni Purāna, Guruda Purāna, and Mahābhārata (Shānti Parva 3/3/6). Correlating with modern medicine, vitiligo-like disorders are documented in the Ebers Papyrus (circa 1500 BCE, Egypt), with Hippocrates often grouping them with leprosy. The term "vitiligo" was later introduced by the Roman physician Aulus Cornelius Celsus in De Medicina^[3]

Classification of Shwitra

1. According to Etiology

Vagbhatta: Divides Shwitra into Agnidagdhaja and Anagnidagdhaja based on causative factors.

Acharya Bhoja: Classifies it into:

Dosha-Atmaja: Arising from vitiated doshas or predisposition to contact factors.

Vranaja: Resulting from improperly healed wounds.

2. According to Origin

Congenital (Sahaja): Charaka mentions “Atigoura” among Ashtanindita Purusha, indicating congenital Shwitra. Vagbhata adds that maternal dietary faults or unfulfilled cravings during pregnancy may lead to congenital Shwitra.

Acquired (Jattotar): Develops after birth due to various etiological factors.

3. According to Pathogenesis

Vitiated Doshas

Vataja: Reddish-white patches with hair changes.

Pittaja: White, smooth, thick patches often with itching.

Dosha-Dushya Involvement: Affects Twak, Mamsa, Meda, and Rakta individually or in combination. When Rakta is involved, it is called Kilasa; when Mamsa is involved, it is called Daruna.

4. According to Clinical Features

Color changes

Aruna Varna: Vata affecting Rakta.

Tamra Varna: Pitta affecting Mamsa.

Shweta Varna: Kapha affecting Meda.

Distribution

Ekadeshaja: Limited to one part.

Sarvadeshaja: Multiple body areas.

Patch Characteristics: Isolated or progressive patches indicate disease advancement.

5. According to Prognosis

Sadhya (Curable)

Asadhya (Incurable)

Nidan Panchak

1. Hetu (Etiology)

Shwitra shares etiological factors with Kushtha. Classical texts describe causes including:

Vitiation of Dhatus: Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Asthi.

Dosha imbalance: Particularly lack of Bhrajak Pitta.

Dietary factors: Incompatible foods, excessive Kapha-promoting substances, maternal diet faults, unfulfilled maternal cravings.

Behavioural and moral factors: Lying, disrespect to teachers, sinful acts, insults, and previous birth sins.

The exact cause of Shwitra remains unclear; however, classical Ayurvedic texts consider its etiology similar to Kushta. It primarily involves vitiation of the three doshas affecting Rakta (blood), Māmsa (muscle), and Meda (fat) dhātus. Factors disturbing these doshas and dhātus are considered causative, with Viruddhāhāra (incompatible foods) and Mithyāhāra (unwholesome foods) playing significant roles. Charaka also mentions moral and behavioral causes, including lying, ingratitude, disrespect to elders or teachers, sinful acts, previous birth karma, and incompatible diet.

In modern medicine, the exact cause of vitiligo is also unknown. Proposed theories include genetic, autoimmune, neurogenic, melanocyte adhesion defects, and biochemical factors, but none are definitive. Onset may be triggered by injury, illness, sunburn, chemical exposure, burns, inflammatory skin conditions, emotional stress, or pregnancy.^[4]

2. Purvaroop(Pre-Clinical Symptoms)

According to Acharya Charak, Acharya Sushrut, Ashtang hriday, Ashtang Sangraha, Madhav Nidan, Bhavprakash following are the purvaroop of Shwitra:

S. NO.	Poovroopa	A-32 Charak	A-33 Sushruta	A-34 A.H.	A-34 A.S.	A-35 M.N.	A-34 B.P.
1.	Sparsha-agyvtam (loss of touch sensation)	+	-	-	-	+	-
2.	Sveda asveda (excessive sweating/absence of sweating).	+	+	+	+	+	+
3.	Vaivarnya (Colour change)	+	+	+	+	-	+
4.	Koth (Rashes)	+	-	-	-	+	-
5.	Lomharsha (Horripilation)	+	+	+	+	-	+
	Kandu (Itching)	+	+	+	+	-	+
7.	Toda (Piercing pain)	-	-	+	+	-	+
8.	Shrama (Physical fatigue)	+	-	+	+	-	-
9.	Klama (Mental Fatigue)	+	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Vranana Amdhikam shoolam	+	-	+	+	-	+
11.	Shigrotpattischirsthic (Early manifestation along with chronicity)	+	-	+	+	+	+
12.	Daah (Burning sensation)	+	-	+	+	-	+
13.	Suptaangata (Numbness)	+	+	+	+	+	+
14.	Kshatavisarpana	-	+	-	-	-	-
15.	Ruksha (Dryness)	-	-	-	+	-	+
16.	Atishlakshna (Smoothness)	-	-	+	+	-	+
17.	Kharasparsha (Roughness)	-	+	+	+	+	+
18.	Asrijah Kashranya (Blackish discoloration of blood)	-	+	+	+	-	+

1. Sparsha-agytvam (loss of touch sensation)
2. Sveda asveda (excessive Sweating/absence of sweating)
3. Vaivarnya (Colour change)
4. Koth (Rashes)
5. Lomharsha (Horripilation)
6. Kandu (Itching)
7. Toda (Piercing pain)
8. Shrama (Physical fatigue)
9. Klama (Mental Fatigue)
10. Vranana Amdhikam shoolam
11. Shigrotpattischirshthic (Early Manifestation along with Chronicity)
12. Daah (Burning sensation)
13. Suptaangata (Numbness)
14. Kshatavisarpana
15. Ruksha (Dryness)
16. Atishlakshna (Smoothness)
17. Kharasparsha (Roughness)
18. Asrijah Kashranya (Blackish discoloration of blood)

In modern medicine, vitiligo is generally asymptomatic but early signs may include:

1. Dry skin
2. Patchy loss of skin color
3. Mild itching
4. Premature whitening or greying of hair

Studies (e.g., Levai) indicate that some vitiligo patients may experience itching even before depigmented patches appear.^[5]

3. Rūpa(Clinical Features)

Ayurvedic Classification Based on Dosha and Dhātu:

Charaka (Subtypes of Kilāsa)^[6]

1. Dārūna: Red (Rakta) patches, involving Rakta dhātu.
2. Arūna: Coppery (Tāmra) patches, involving Māmsa dhātu.
3. Shwitra: White (Shweta) patches, involving Meda dhātu.

Sushruta^[7]

1. Vātaja: Round, reddish-brown, dry, with hair loss.
2. Pittaja: Lotus-petal colored, burning sensation.
3. Kaphaja: White, thick, unctuous, with itching.

Vāgbhatta^[8]

1. Vataja: Light red, dry, localized in Rakta dhātu.
2. Pittaja: Coppery, burning, hair follicle destruction, localized in Māmsa dhātu.
3. Kaphaja: White, thick, heavy, with itching, localized in Meda dhātu.

Other Classical Views

Shwitra and Kilāsa are largely synonymous; some authors differentiate based on patch color, depth of Dhātu involvement, or severity.

Bhoja classified Shwitra by origin: Doshaja (Ātmaja or Paraja) and Vranaja (from wounds, burns, or injuries).

Hārīta^[9]: Vitiated Vata and Pitta affecting Rakta dhātu produces yellowish-white (Pāndura) patches.

Kāshyapa: Any white discoloration of skin is considered Shwitra.

Modern Correlation (Vitiligo)

Shwitra presents as white, red, or coppery patches on the skin or mucous membranes, usually without exudation. Leukotrichia may be present. Patients may occasionally experience burning, heaviness, numbness, hair loss, or central swelling within the patches.

Lesions are typically whitish, non-scaly macules with distinct margins.

Discoloration often begins on sun-exposed areas (hands, feet, face, lips).

Types include

Segmental Vitiligo (SV): Limited, 10–15% of cases

Non-segmental Vitiligo (NSV): Widespread, ~80% of cases, with subtypes including acrofacial, mucosal, generalized, universal, mixed, punctate, minor (children), and follicular.^[10]

Shwitra/Vitiligo can thus be understood as a depigmentary disorder with varied presentations depending on Dosha involvement, depth of Dhātu, and lesion characteristics.

4. Samprāpti (Pathogenesis)

Though the Samprāpti (pathogenesis) of Shwitra is not directly explained in the Ayurvedic classics, it can be interpreted based on the general Nidānas of Kushtha and the Tridoṣha involvement described across the Samhitās.

Frequent indulgence in causative factors such as Viruddhāhāra (incompatible diet), Mithyāchara (improper conduct), and other Kushtha-nidānas lead to the formation of Āma (metabolic toxins). This Āma vitiates all three Doṣas—Vāta, Pitta, and Kapha, which then mix with Rasa dhātu and spread sequentially through deeper Dhātus. When these Doṣas reach the Twak (skin) through Tiryakgata Sirās (capillary channels), they lodge in the Tāmra layer due to Sthānavaiguṇya (localized susceptibility) and Khavaiguṇya (tissue deformity), obstructing Rasavaha and Raktavaha Srotas.

This leads to the depletion of Bhrājaka Pitta, resulting in Twak Shvetatā (loss of normal skin color). As the process progresses, Rakta, Māmsa, and Meda Dhātus become affected, producing reddish, coppery, or white discoloration respectively. Among the Doṣas, Udāna Vāta and Bhrājaka Pitta play a key role in color maintenance, while Vyāna Vāta aids the spread of Doṣas with Rasa dhātu.

Classical Descriptions

Charaka Samhitā

The three Doṣas viliate Twak, Rakta, and Lasikā, giving rise to seven Mahākushthas and eleven Kṣudra Kushthas. Hence, Shwitra occurs when Doṣa–Dhātu Sammūrchanā (pathogenic interaction) happens in these tissues.

Suśruta Samhitā

The aggravated Vāta carries Pitta and Kapha through Sirās over the body surface and deposits them in the Twak. The affected regions develop patches, and neglected pathology further contaminates deeper Dhātus. However, Sushruta notes that Shwitra primarily remains limited to the skin and is Aparisrāvi (non-exudative).

Aṣṭāṅga Saṅgraha

Pāpa Karma (sins from previous births) vitiate Doṣas, which circulate through Tiryak Sirās, affecting Rakta, Māmsa, and Twak. The vitiated elements cause discoloration, manifesting as Kushtha in the form of patches.

Aṣṭāṅga Hṛidaya

Improper diet, Viruddhāhāra, unethical behavior, and Adharmika Karma vitiate Tridoṣas, which circulate to Twak, Lasikā, Rakta, and Māmsa Dhātus via Tiryak Sirās, causing laxity and discoloration of the skin, leading to Kushtha Roga.

Samprapti Ghatak-(favourable things for disease)

- a) Doshas: Vata-especially Udana Vayu.
- b) Dushya: Rasa, Rakta, Mansa, Meda.
- c) Srotas: Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mansavaha, Medovaha.
- d) Sroto Dushti Lakshan: Sanga, Vimarga-Gaman.
- e) Marga: Bahya Rog Marga.
- f) Gati: Tiryaka.
- g) Adhishshthana: Twacha.
- h) Chirkari.

Investigations and Biomarkers in Vitiligo (Leucoderma)

Vitiligo is often linked with various autoimmune and endocrine disorders; hence, relevant laboratory investigations are recommended. Routine hematological and urine tests, along with specific immunological markers such as Anti-nuclear antibody (ANA), Anti-thyroid peroxidase antibody (ATPO), Anti-parietal gastric cell antibody (APGC), Anti-thyroglobulin antibody (ATG), and thyroid profile (TSH, FT4) are useful. Additionally, fasting blood glucose, Vitamin B12, and folic acid levels may help identify associated metabolic or nutritional abnormalities.

Recent studies have identified several biomarkers that reflect disease activity and pathogenesis. These include serum homocysteine, tyrosinase/melanin levels, altered serum miRNA expression, oxidative stress indicators, mitochondrial dysfunction, lymphocyte-mediated immune responses, DNA damage markers, and trace elements like serum zinc. Genetic, neural, and apoptotic mechanisms are also believed to contribute to the development and progression of vitiligo.^[11]

Prognosis (Sādhya–Asādhyatā)

Shwitra (Vitiligo) is considered an obstinate skin disorder that is generally difficult to cure. However, its prognosis varies depending on factors such as duration, extent, site of lesions, and changes in hair colour over the affected area.

According to Āchārya Charaka: Shwitra with no red hairs (Arakta Lomavat), thin or small patches (Tanu), pale colour (Pāndu), of recent origin (Naiva), and slightly elevated in the centre is Sādhya (curable). In contrast, lesions with red hair (Rakta Lomavat), thick or extensive patches, indistinct margins (Parasparato Abhinna), and chronicity beyond one year are Asādhya (incurable).

According to Āchārya Suśruta: Lesions located on the lips, palms, soles, or genital regions (Anta Jātam), associated with red hair and burn origin (Agnidagdha), or those that are confluent (Sambandha Mandalam) are considered incurable.

According to Āchārya Vāgbhata: Patches that are small, newly formed, with black hair, non-confluent, and not caused by burns are curable. Conversely, lesions with white hair, chronicity, extensive spread, or occurrence over genital organs, palms, soles, and lips are incurable, even if recently developed.

Prognosis also depends on the predominant Dosha:

Vātaja type – difficult to cure

Pittaja type – more difficult

Kaphaja type – almost incurable

Clinically, limited and recent lesions, especially on the face and trunk in younger individuals, respond well to therapy. In contrast, long-standing and extensive vitiligo, particularly involving lips, hands, feet, and genital areas, shows poor prognosis. Complete depigmentation indicates irreversible pigment loss and is generally considered Asādhya.[12]

Complications

Although vitiligo itself does not progress into other diseases, affected individuals are more prone to certain complications. These include psychological and social distress, sunburn and increased skin cancer risk, ocular issues such as inflammation of the iris or vision disturbances, and hearing impairment.

Vitiligo may also be associated with other autoimmune disorders like thyroid dysfunction, Addison's disease, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, type-1 diabetes, and pernicious anaemia. While most patients do not develop these conditions, relevant tests may be advised to rule them out.^[13]

5. Chikitsa Karma (Principles of Management of Shwitra Roga)

There is no exclusive Chikitsā Sūtra described in the classics for Shwitra; however, Acharyas have considered it under Kushtha Chikitsa. The general line of management includes Samshodhana (bio-purification) followed by Samshamana (palliative therapy).

1. Samshodhana Chikitsa (Purificatory Therapy)

Both Charaka and Vagbhata emphasize Samshodhana as the first line of treatment. Procedures like Snehana, Swedana, Vamana, and Virechana help in expelling vitiated Doshas. Raktamokshana is also indicated, especially when Rakta Dhatu is involved.

Depending on the Dhatu involved

Tvak level – Shodhana and Lepa Karma

Rakta level – Raktamokshana and Kashaya Pana

Mamsa/Medo level – Bhallataka, Guggulu, Khadira, Asana, etc. are advised.

In Asthi Dhatu involvement, the disease becomes Asādhya.

Vagbhata recommends Vamana fortnightly, Virechana monthly, Shirovirechana every 3 days, and Raktamokshana every 6 months. Exposure to mild sunlight post-therapy is also beneficial.

2. Samshamana Chikitsa (Palliative Therapy)

Internal and external medications aim to pacify vitiated Doshas and restore pigmentation.

Internal formulations include:

Kwatha: Khadiradi, Manjishthadi, Dhātryadi

Churna: Bakuchi, Panchanimba, Triphala

Vati/Guggulu: Swayambhuva Guggulu, Shashilekha Vati, Vijayeshwara Rasa

Ghritha: Mahātikta Ghritha, Somaraji Ghritha, Bhallataka Ghritha

Taila: Somaraji Taila, Marichyadi Taila, Panchanana Taila, Jyotishmati Taila

Asava/Arishta: Khadirarishta, Sarivadyasava, Madhvasava

Rasaushadhi: Gandhak Rasayana, Rasamanikya, Talkeshwar Rasa

External therapies

Lepa (topical applications) like Bakuchi Lepa, Manahshiladi Lepa, Triphala Lepa with sunlight exposure promote melanogenesis.

3. Rasayana Chikitsa (Rejuvenative Therapy)

To prevent recurrence and enhance immunity, Rasayana drugs like Guduchi, Haridra, Amalaki, Bhallataka, Manjistha, Chitraka, and Bhringaraja are recommended.

4. Nidana Parivarjana (Avoidance of Causative Factors)

Avoidance of Viruddhahara and Mithyahāra Vihara is crucial. Preventive care and lifestyle correction form the foundation of management.

5. Deepana-Pachana (Enhancing Digestion and Metabolism)

To eliminate Āma and correct Agni, formulations like Trikatu Churna, Hingwāshtaka, and Chitrakādi Vati are useful.

6. Yogic and Lifestyle Therapy

Pranayama (Nādisodhana, Bhrāmari, Sitali) and Asanas (Padmasana, Suryanamaskara) help reduce stress, balance immunity, and support pigmentation.

7. Pathya–Apathya (Diet and Lifestyle Regulations)

Pathya: Shali rice, Mudga dal, Tikta Rasa dravya, Jangala mamsa, Ghee, Nimba, Triphala.

Apathya: Amla rasa, Dadhi, Dugdha, Fish, Guda, and Taila.

Modern Correlation

Modern management focuses on achieving uniform skin tone via re-pigmentation or depigmentation. Treatment options include topical corticosteroids, phototherapy, systemic agents, and surgical methods.^[14] The combination of multiple therapies yields better results, though prognosis remains variable.

The Ayurvedic management of Shwitra aims at eliminating vitiated Doshas, purifying the system, restoring pigmentation, and preventing recurrence through Shodhana, Shamana, Rasayana, and Pathya-Apathya, supplemented with Yoga and Sun exposure.

DISCUSSION

Vitiligo is a chronic depigmentary disorder causing white patches on the skin, leading to cosmetic and psychological concerns. In Ayurveda, it is classified as Shwitra or Kilāsa under Kushta Roga. The disease is primarily caused by the vitiation of Tridoṣa—mainly Kapha and Pitta—along with involvement of Rakta and Meda Dhātu. Factors such as Viruddhāhāra, Mithyāhāra, and lifestyle errors contribute to its onset. Pathogenesis involves impairment of Bhrajaka Pitta, leading to loss of pigmentation. Classical texts describe varieties of Shwitra based on color and chronicity, which can be correlated with modern Vitiligo types. Management focuses on Nidāna Parivarjana, Shodhana and Shamana therapies, along with internal and external Ayurvedic formulations to restore Doṣa balance and promote repigmentation.

CONCLUSION

Shwitra is a Kushtha type disorder marked by non-exudative white patches caused by Kapha-dominant Tridosha vitiation. Viruddhāhāra and Mithyāhāra are major causative factors. Chronic cases become difficult to cure, while timely Shodhana followed by Shamana therapy gives better results. Ayurveda offers a holistic approach to Shwitra management, which requires further scientific validation through modern research.

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